

MĀṆḌHAḶ PLATES OF VĀKĀṬAKA RUDRASENA II, YEAR 5

By

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The plates in question were reported found in rather curious circumstances. In June 1982 a few Nagpur dailies carried the news of the discovery of a set of copper-plates in the village of Māṇḍhaḷ, some seventy-five kms. from Nagpur in the Umred taluka of the Nagpur District. According to the news item, these plates were found concealed under a block of stone and were acquired by the local organisation called Māṇḍhaḷ Itihās Samśodhan Samiti. Seeing the news and without wasting much time, one of us (C. S. G.) proceeded to Māṇḍhaḷ, contacted office-bearers of the Samiti and got from them dependable information concerning the circumstances leading to the find of this record. These plates were reportedly found in a field while ploughing and for some reason were concealed under a stone-block. They were subsequently located by two labourers employed under the Employment Guarantee Scheme while breaking pebbles and from them they were acquired by the Samiti. And at a simple function these plates were presented to the then Vice-Chancellor of the Nagpur University for its Department of Ancient Indian History, Culture and Archaeology with which they had become familiar in course of the excavations conducted at the site a few years earlier. These excavations had resulted in the discovery of three other copper-plate grants of the Vākāṭakas, viz., one of the sixteenth year of Pravarasena II¹ and two of his grandsons issued in his second and tenth years,² which were found in a terracotta pot covered with a lid in the *adhiṣṭhāna* of a brick temple belonging to the Vākāṭaka period remains of which were uncovered in course of the archaeological work at the site. Māṇḍhaḷ has, thus, the unique distinction of yielding as many as four of the Vākāṭaka copper-plate charters, the present one being the earliest of them all.

The record under publication is one of king Rudrasena II of the Nandivardhana-Pravarapura branch of the Vākāṭaka dynasty. This is so far the only known copper-plate grant of Rudrasena II and the earliest disco-

¹ Ajay Mitra Shastri, "Māṇḍhaḷ Copper-Plate Charter of Pravarasena II, Year 16", *EI*, XLI (1975-76, pub. 1989), pp. 68-76.

² Ajay Mitra Shastri, "Māṇḍhaḷ Plates of Pṛithivīshēna II, Years 2 and 10", *ibid.*, pp. 159-80.

vered to date of the Nandivardhana-Pravarapura branch, which, *inter alia*, makes it highly important.

The inscription is incised on a set of four plates of copper, measuring 11.5 cms. high and 21 cms. broad. The first and the last plates bear writing only on one (inner) side, while the remaining two plates are engraved on both sides. The plates are strung together on a circular copper-ring passing through a hole made on them in the left margin. The seal attached to the ring is now missing with the result that we know absolutely nothing about the nature and contents of the inscription and the device/devices, if any, on Ruadrasena II's seals affixed to his copper-plate charters.

The record consists in all of thirty-four lines of writing which are distributed on the inscribed sides of the plates as follows : six lines each on the inner side of the first plate and the first side of the second plate, seven on the second side of the second plate, and five each on the remaining incised faces of the plates. Although the edges of the plates are neither raised nor thickened, the writing is generally well-preserved and clear except at a few places on the first plate in the first three lines where it has become somewhat indistinct and doubtful due to some unintelligent modern attempts by the finders of the set at cleaning the plates which brought them in contact with fire resulting in slightly damaging the writing.

The inscription is incised in what is commonly called box-headed variety of the Brāhmī alphabet prevalent in Central India from about the fourth century A. D. in which most of the Vākāṭaka inscriptions are engraved.^{2a} The present plates are very important and crucial from this point of view as they happen to be the earliest known copper-plate grant of the Nandivardhana branch of the Vākāṭakas and might reasonably be expected to give us some idea of the earlier^{2b} form of the box-headed characters in so far as the Vākāṭakas are concerned. However, curiously enough, the variety appears in a fully developed form even in this first known charter of this branch of the dynasty. But the following points may still be noted. The boxes are conspicuous by their absence in the case of the letters *l*, *e*, *kha*, *ṅ*, *ñ* and *la*. In some cases on the letter *ja* there is no box (e. g. *jala*, line 1; *mahārāja*, line 7; *-ārjjava*, line 8; *-jñay-ājñāpayitavyā*, line 13; *-rāja-datta-*,

^{2a} Prabhāvatīguptā's Puṇe plates and the Rāmṭek inscription referring to Prabhāvatīguptā's death are the only exceptions.

^{2b} According to some scholars *OII*, V (1963), pp. 1ff., the Devṭek inscription belongs to Rudrasēna I. However, there is nothing to indicate its attribution to the first ruler of this name.

line 27; *-pajitān*, line 29). However, in other cases the *akṣara ja* has a square box attached on top or back of the upper portion (e. g. *-vājina*, line 3). The letter *ba* is sometimes without a box (e. g. *-rbbala-*, line 14; *brāhmaṇā-*, line 19) and in other cases has a small square attached to the left vertical in the middle (e. g. *bādhā-* and *brāhmaṇair-*, line 26). The boxes are generally square, but we also have some rare instances of rectangular boxes as on *ga* in *yoga-* in line 2 which may be contrasted with the square box on top of the same letter in *bhagavatō* in the inaugural line. The initial *ṣ* with a rectangular box attached to the bottom of the vertical stroke on left bears a close resemblance to the letter *ca* and would have been confused with it but for the box-head which is attached to the latter but is conspicuous by its absence in the former case. There are two different forms of *ga*: in one form the square box is attached to the angular top of the letter which looks like a triangle open at the bottom as in *bhagavatō* (line 1) and another with a rather rectangular box on top of a somewhat rounded letter with a slight curve at the left bottom-line as in *yoga-* (line 2). For the letter *j* we have different forms: in some cases it closely resembles the angular English letter 'E' without any box (e. g. *Rāja-vamśā-* and *jala-*, line 6; *jala-* and *mahārāja*, line 7; *saty-ārjjava-*, line 8; *rāja-datta-*, line 27; *-pajitā-*, line 29); sometimes the lower part is turned into an angular rectangle open to right and the upper portion is in the form of a smaller square placed over the lower rectangle slightly to the right and a squarish box attached to it on left upper part (e. g. *-vājina-*, line 3). The letter *dh* has two different forms: one with a somewhat flattened right part (e. g. *Yudhi-*, line 13) and the other with a completely rounded circle (e. g. *putr-ādhi-*, line 13), both sometimes met with in the same line showing clearly that the difference is purely accidental. In the case of the letter *bh* we sometimes have a rectangular form with a short horizontal stroke attached to the bottom of the left vertical stroke (e. g. *Bhairava*, line 5; *bhagavata-*, line 11; *bhaṣā-*, line 13), and a square form without the horizontal stroke at the bottom of the left vertical as in *-bhakta-*, line 5. The fact that the two forms of the letter are met with not only in the same line but in the same expression would show that the difference is quite unintentional and not much value need be attached to it.

The language is Sanskrit which is quite incorrect at places grammatically. The entire record is in prose except only a single imprecatory stanza towards the end in lines 31-32. As for orthography, attention may be invited to the following points. The consonant preceding the subscript (*caḥkrā-* line 2; *parākkramā-*, line 6; *caḥkra-*, line 11) and following the superscript (*ṣk-ārjjava-*, line 1; *-āptoryyama-* for *-āptoryyāma-*, line 3; *-ārjjava-* and *ṣauryya-*, line 8; *dharmma-*, lines 9; 14, 14-15; 27; *-nairmmalyā-*, line

9; -r=Vvākāṭakānā-, line 10; -pūrvva-, lines 12, 13, 15, 18; -r=bbala-, and t-ārttha-, line 14; -kāryya- line 17; kuryyāma and -ṅair=vṣditasya, line 26, etc.) *repha* is often reduplicated. But we also have some instances where the reduplication of the preceding consonant is conspicuous by its absence (e. g. *putra-pautriṅaḥ*, line 10). We also find the letter *v* following an *anusvāra* is sometimes reduplicated (*savvatsarṣ* for *samvatsarṣ*, line 32). In a few cases dental *n* is used instead of the palatal one *ṅ* (e. g. -ṣṣṇa for -ṣṣṇa, line 11; *alavana-* for *alavaṅa-*, line 22; -Viṣṇu for -Viṣṇu, line 30). There are also cases of the non-observance of sandhi rules (e. g. -dhāriṅaḥ *dṣva-*, line 2; *samrājah Vākāṭakā-*, line 4; *sūnoḥ sūnoḥ atyanta-*, lines 4-5; *sūnoḥ saty-ārjjava-*, line 8; *vaḥ yathṣ-*, line 13; -*kasya apara-* and *Śaṅkhi-kayoḥ uttara-*, line 15; *datyā udaka-*, line 18; *tad=yathā akara-*, lines 20-21; *prāvṣyaḥ apara-* and *balivarddaḥ a-puṣpa-*, line 21; -*sandohaḥ a-cār-*, lines 21-22; *s-opanidhiḥ sa-klṛpt-opaklṛptaḥ ā-candrā-*, line 23, etc.). It is not impossible that some of these cases may have been deliberate for the sake of clarity and non-confusion and may be contrasted with examples of the observance of these rules where no such confusion is involved (-*gaṇayamānas =svalpām=api*, line 25). There are no abbreviations. Punctuation marks are not used where one should expect them, and the only punctuation is used where it is not required (line 11). However, at the end we have a *visarga*-like mark following the auspicious formula *siddhir=astu* (line 34) which may actually have been intended to mark the conclusion of the record.

As in most other grants of the Vākāṭakes, the inscription begins with the auspicious word *siddham* ('success has been achieved') followed by the word *dṛṣṭam* (seen) which is indicative of its authenticity and is engraved in between the first and second lines on left. Next we are told that the grant recorded in inscription was made at message or command (*sandēśa*³) of the supreme god (*deva-deva*) Mondasvamin who is described as carrying a conch-shell (*śaṅkha*), a wheel (*cakra*) and a sword (*asi*) and resting in the *yoga-nidrā*⁴ (meditative sleep) on the body of the snake-king called Ananta⁵

³ The word *sandēśa* is generally taken to mean 'message' but may also connote 'order' or 'command'. Whatever be the meaning of the term in the instant case, it appears to allude to divine inspiration, perhaps in a dream, to make the donation in question.

⁴ This is a technical term referring to 'a state of half meditation and half sleep' and especially alludes to Viṣṇu's sleep at the end of a Yuga' and is used here in this sense. See Monier Monier-Williams, *A Sanskrit-English Dictionary*, Reprint, Delhi, 1981, p. 847.

⁵ The name of the snake-king (*nāga-rāja*) looks like Nanna, but it is possible to take the second *akṣara* as *nta* as well as there is often confusion between the letters *t* and *n* and taking *nāga-rājñō-nantasya* together, we may split up the expression into *nāga-* (Continued on the next page.)

in the waters of the ocean. This is obviously an allusion to the *śeṣa-śāyin* form of Viṣṇu about which more will be said in the sequel. The genealogy of the Vākāṭakas that follows generally agrees with that found in other copper-plate grants of the Nandivardhana-Pravarapura branch. There is only slight difference in the phraseology at some places.⁶ The inscription aims at registering Rudrasena II's grant of the four villages named Selludruha, Acchabhallikā, Saragrāmakā and Aragrāmakā to some Brāhmaṇas belonging to various *gotra*-s and *carāṇa*-s and engaged in study, the donees being left unnamed. The pieces of land earlier granted⁷ in favour of a couple of monasteries (*adhivāsa*-s) of the *carāṇa*-s (Vedic schools) of the Sātvatas belonging to Vatsagulma) were excavated. These villages were situated in eastern *mārga* of Padmapura and were bordered by Kurudumbhaka on the east, the two villages called Śaṅkhikā on the south, Bābbaikā on the west and Phukudumbhaka on the north. These villages were evidently converted into an *agrāhāra*. In this connection it is interesting to mention that the grant recorded in the Riddhapur plates of Prabhāvatī Guptā⁸ was also meant for a group of unnamed Brāhmaṇas though they are said to have belonged to a particular *gotra* (Parāśara) and Vedic *śākhā* (Taittirīya). The government officers and privileges and exemptions mentioned in connection with the present grant are almost identical with those encountered in other charters of Vākāṭakas. These are followed by an imprecatory stanza in the Anuṣṭubh

(Continued from p. 146.)

rājñah Anantasya. It is quite possible, however, that the intended reading was actually *nāga-rājño Nannasya* as it is found. But it would also make no difference in the meaning as Ananta is known to have been transformed popularly into Nanna as, for example, in Nanna-Nārāyaṇa-bhaṭṭāraka who figures as the donee in the Khalimpur plates of the Pāla king Dharmapāla. See *EI*, IV (1900-01), p. 250, text-line 50 and p. 254, note 3. This would show that the name Ananta had been corrupted into Nanna as early as the fifth century A. D. The name Nanna met with in numerous Śarabhapuriya, Pāṇḍuvamśin and Rāṣṭrakūṭa inscriptions would show the popularity of this form during the ancient and early mediaeval times.

⁶ Rudrasena II, for example, is referred to in our record as *bhagavataś-cakra-lakṣma-pratiṣṭhita-śūsana*, viz., his authority was established by the god with wheel for his emblem, i. e. Viṣṇu, whereas in other later grants of the family he is styled *bhagavataś-cakra-pūneh prasād-opārjita-śrī-samudaya*, viz. his abundant prosperity was caused by the favour of the wheel-bearing god, i. e. Viṣṇu. In line 8 in the description of Pṛthivīseṇa I the sectarian expression *atyanta-Māheśvarasya* has been added in subsequent records. The omission in the present record may be due to oversight. These are the major differences between the present grant and later records of the Vākāṭakas of this branch. Other differences are of a minor nature and will be noticed in notes on the text.

⁷ *Apūrva-datti* in the original. Our attention to its importance was drawn by Dr. K. V. Ramesh, for which we are thankful to him.

⁸ V. V. Mirashi, "Inscriptions of the Vākāṭakas," *CII*, V (1963), pp. 33ff.

metre ascribed to Vyāsa. Next comes the *date* of the record which is the *seventh day of the sixth fortnight of the rainy season in the fifth year, apparently of the donor's reign*. The charter was written by *Senāpati Vibhīṣaṇa*, while the order in respect of the grant was issued by the king himself (*svamukh-ājñaptih*). At the end we find the auspicious formula *siddhir-astu*, 'let there be success'.

The inscription is of *inestimable value* from several points of view. Till now the fragmentary Deotek (Chanda District, Maharashtra) stone inscription of Rudrasena⁹ was supposed to be the earliest record of the Nandivardhana-Pravarapura branch of the Vākāṭakas. However, apart from its fragmentary character, it does not afford any definite evidence to enable its undoubted attribution to the first or second ruler of this name, though it is generally ascribed to Rudrasena I. Viewed from this angle, this is the oldest known definitely ascribable record of this branch, and certainly the first known copper-plate charter of this branch of the dynasty. Secondly, as no dated record of Rudrasena II was available so far, there was no means of determining the length of his reign which was conjecturally fixed variously by historians. But the present record which was issued in the fifth year of his reign, leaves no doubt about the fact that he ruled at least for five years. However, we still have no means of ascertaining as to how long he continued to rule after the date of this inscription. Thirdly, the employment of the season date, which is met with only in a few records while others give dates in months as now, is of great interest.¹⁰ It is noteworthy in this connection that the earliest known grant of the Vatsagulma branch, viz., Basim plates of Vindhyaśakti II,¹¹ is also dated in season. Fourthly, *Senāpati Vibhīṣaṇa*, who was responsible for writing this grant, has been brought to light by this record for the first time. Fifthly, this epigraph gives us an idea of the evolution of the draft of the official charters of the Nandivardhana-Pravarapura branch of the dynasty up to the time of Rudrasena II.¹²

⁹ *Ibid.*, pp. 1ff.

¹⁰ These season dates in all likelihood were adopted by the Vākāṭaka from the Sātavāhanas who were their predecessors in their adopted region. Most of the recently discovered Vākāṭaka records contain season dates which are consequently not so rare as supposed earlier and their use, therefore, cannot be taken to indicate an early date for records containing them. For the use of season dates as a criterion of an early date see V. V. Mirashi, "The Date of the Malhārā Plates of Ādityarāja", *JESI*, V (1978), p. 2; and for its criticism, see Ajay Mitra Shastri, "The Malhārā Plates of Ādityarāja: A Re-appraisal", *ibid.*, IV, p. 34. The usual month-dates met with in the Vākāṭaka records were probably due to the Gupta influence.

¹¹ *CII*, V (1963), pp. 93 ff.

¹² It appears that the draft had almost been standardised by the time of Rudrasena II and copied with only some minor alterations in later grants of the family. For some of the major differences, see note 6 above and for minor differences, note on the text.

The present charter is of considerable interest for religious history as well. That it is a Vaiṣṇavite record should be clear from its contents. The practice of naming a divine image or shrine after a personal or place name was quite popular in ancient India and continues to be so even today, and while names ending in Īśa, Īśvara and Śiva were prevalent among the Śaivas, the Vaiṣṇavas favoured *svāmin*-ending names. And since Monda does not look like a personal name, the god Mondasvāmin appears to have been christened after the locality where the temple was situated. It is noteworthy in this connection that there still exist villages named Maudā and Ḍonger Maudā in the vicinity of Māṇḍhaḷ, the findspot of the record. It may, thus, be concluded that the temple of Mondasvāmin was situated in this area. Let us hope that future explorations would throw more light on this problem. It is also pertinent to note in this connection that the excavations conducted at Māṇḍhaḷ have thrown up some beautiful early Vākāṭaka sculptures of Vaiṣṇava affiliation.¹³ It may, therefore, be concluded that during the early Vākāṭaka period the region round Māṇḍhaḷ was an important centre of Bhāgavatism-Vaiṣṇavism. Rudrasena II alone among the early Vākāṭaka rulers¹⁴ was a devout votary of Vaiṣṇavism, and it is stated in our record as well as the later official charters of the family that his authority was established by the wheel bearing god, i. e. Viṣṇu.¹⁵ Other later official charters of the family say the same thing in somewhat different words, viz. his abundant prosperity was acquired through the grace of the god bearing a wheel in his hand (*cakra-pāṇi*).¹⁶ It is very likely, therefore, that he played a pivotal role in popularising the Bhāgavata religion in this region. It is also not impossible, though by no means certain, that at least some of the temples brought to light at Māṇḍhaḷ as a result of archaeological work were erected by Rudrasena II, especially as the grant in question has been discovered at the locality. In this respect Rudrasena II and Pṛithivīśeṇa II, who were the only *parama-Bhāgavata*-s among the Vākāṭaka monarchs, stand in contrast to the rest of the rulers of the Nandivardhana-Pravarapura branch who were all devout Śaivas. It is very likely that this religious transformation was effected as a result of the close contact with the Imperial Guptas as a result of Prabhāvatī Guptā's marriage with Rudrasena II.

The description of Śeṣa-śāyin form of god Viṣṇu under the name Mondasvāmin is also of great interest for studying the development of Viṣṇu's

¹³ See Ajay Mitra Shastri, "Māṇḍhaḷ Utkhanana", *Vidarbha Samśodhana Maṇḍala Vārṣika*, 1977, pp. 142ff.

¹⁴ The only other Vākāṭaka king described as *parama-Bhāgavata* is the last known member of the Nandivardhana-Pravarapura branch, Pṛthivīśeṇa II.

^{15,16} For the originals, see note 6 above.

iconography. In so far as we are aware, this is one of the oldest datable description of this form, and it will be in the fitness of things to trace its sculptural parallels satisfying the account in full.^{16a} The well-known Bhītargāon and Deogadh Anantaśayana panels, which are the earliest known so far are somewhat later than our inscription and do not tally with our description in so far as the *āyudha*-s (emblems or weapons) held in his hands are concerned.¹⁷ The South Indian Śeṣa-śayana or Ananta-śayana panels, popularly called Raṅga-nātha or Raṅga-svāmin, are of a considerably later period.

In ancient India a great controversy raged regarding the Vedic or non-Vedic character of the Sātvatas, who were the people among whom lord Kṛṣṇa was born. Some of the Vaiṣṇava Āgamas adduce arguments to prove their Vedic affiliation. The reference to the Sātvata as a *carāṇa* seems to indicate that its Vedicism had become established at least among the Pāñcārātras, by the early fifth century A. D. in the Deccan. As the two monasteries of the Sātvatas mentioned in our record were situated in the Māṇḍhaḷ region, it may be justifiably concluded that this area was an important centre of their activities. And since these Sātvatas originally hailed from Vatsagulma or Basim, the Vatsagulma region must also have been an important centre of this sect.¹⁸ In fact, it appears that the seat of the Sātvatas at Vatsagulma worked with a missionary zeal and sent out missions to other places.

Before we conclude, something must be said about the place-names mentioned in our record. The donated villages are stated to have been situated in the *pūrva-mārga* of Padmapura. That the word *mārga* when joined to a place-name stands for an administrative division is shown by the Mahurjhari plates of Pṛthivīṣeṇa II recording the grant of the village

^{16a} Another reference to an eight-armed Śeṣaśayana Viṣṇu which is older by a few years, is met with in the Bāgh Plate dated year 47 of *Mahārāja* Bhulunḍa. For the discussion of the reference, see Ajay Mitra Shastri, "Śeṣaśayana Viṣṇu - earliest evidence".

¹⁷ For these panels, see J. N. Banerjea, *The Development of Hindu Iconography*, second edition, Calcutta, 1956, pp. 406-07. In the Deogadh panel we find Cakra-puruṣa (personified *Cakra*) standing behind Lakṣmī, and a few of what are taken to be attendants, it has been argued, may represent personified *āyudha*-s.

¹⁸ The adjective *Vātsagulmaka* used in the text for these monasteries would ordinarily mean 'belonging to' or 'situated at' Vatsagulma. This Vatsagulma has been identified with modern Basim in the Akola District which was the capital of the Vatsagulma branch of the Vākāṭakas. But as the grant in question belongs to the Nandivardhana-Pravarapura branch of the dynasty which could not make a land-grant in or near the capital of the other branch, the expression in question has to be taken to mean 'hailing from Vatsagulma'.

Jamalakhetaka said to have been situated in the Jamalakhetaka-*mārga*.¹⁹ As the Māsod plates of the nineteenth year of the reign of Pravarasena II refer to the *apara-mārga* of Padmapura,²⁰ it may be reasonably concluded that the administrative division named after Padmapura was divided into two parts - eastern (*pūrva*) and western (*apara*), with the town of Padmapura as its headquarters. The chief place of this division cannot be identified at present. However since Matsyadraha or Māsod in the Kāṭol Tahsil of the Nagpur District granted through the above-mentioned Māsod plates is stated to have been situated in the *apara-mārga* of this division, the Kāṭol region may be taken to have been included in this *mārga*, though at present it is not possible to determine its extent. The Padmapura-*pūrva-mārga* must, therefore, be located to the east of Masod, though how far east, we cannot be sure. In view of this fact Padmapura, the chief town of this unit, should be looked for somewhere in the Nagpur-Wardha region. Whether this Padmapura had something to do with the homonymous town mentioned as the place of issue of an incomplete Vākāṭaka grant found at Durg²¹ (chief town of a district in Madhya Pradesh) is something that cannot be stated definitely at present. It has been identified by V. V. Mirashi with modern Padampur near Āmgāon in the Bhaṇḍārā District.²² This deserves a re-consideration in the light of the evidence afforded by the Māṇḍhāl plates of Rudrasena II and the Māsod grant of Praverasena II. Monda and Vatsagulma may be identified with one of the villages called Maudā or Ḍoṅgar Maudā near Māṇḍhāl and Bāsim in the Akolā district respectively. Selludraha is perhaps identical with modern Selḍoh and Saragrāmaka with Suregāon in the Wardhā District and Aragrāma with modern Āregaon in the Nagpur District. Basing on these identifications we can only be sure that the Padmapura-*mārga* comprised roughly the northwestern part of the Nagpur District and the north-eastern portion of the Wardha District. Other localities are not identifiable now.

¹⁹ V. B. Kolte, "Māhūrzarī Plates of Pṛthivīśena II", *ABORI* LIII (1972), p. 193, text-lines 27-28.

²⁰ Ajay Mitra Shastri and Chandrashekhar Gupta, "Māsod Copper-Plate Charter of Pravarasena II," *JESI* X (1983), p. 113, text-line 19; *ibid.*, XI, p. 114,

²¹ *CII*, V (1963), p. 78, text-line 1. ²² *Ibid.*, p. 78.

MĀṆḌHAL PLATES OF VĀKĀṬAKA RUDRASENA II, YR 5

FIRST PLATE

SECOND PLATE : FIRST SIDE

SECOND PLATE : SECOND SIDE

THIRD PLATE ; FIRST SIDE

THIRD PLATE : SECOND SIDE

FOURTH PLATE

FIRST PLATE

- 1 सिद्धम् [। *] दृष्टम्²³ [। *] भगवतो²⁴ एकाण्णव सलिलविस्तारितनागराज्ञो नन्नस्य²⁵ तस्य वच स्फुटफटाजल²⁶ भोगशायि-
- 2 योगनिद्रामुपगतस्य शङ्खचक्रकालिधारिणः²⁷ देवद(दे)वस्य मोन्दस्वामिनस्सन्देशात् [। *] अग्निष्टो-
- 3 ²⁸माप्तोय्य(र्या)मा(मो)कथ्यबोडश्यतिर(रा)त्रवाजयेयवृद्धस्वतिसवसायस्कचतुरधमेधया-
जिन(नो)विष्णु-
- 4 वृद्धसगोत्रस्य सम्राजः (जो)²⁹ वाकाटकानाम्महाराजश्रीप्रवरस(से)नस्य सूनोः (नो)-
स्सूनोः³⁰
- 5 अत्यन्तस्वामिमहाभैरवभक्तस्य अ(अं)सभारसन्निवेशितशिवलिङ्गोद्बहनशिवसुपरितुष्टसमु-
- 6 त्पादितराजवंशानाम्पराक्क्रमाधिगतभागीरथ्यमलजलमूर्द्धानभिषिक्तानां दशाश्वमेधावभृथ-

SECOND PLATE : FIRST SIDE

- 7 स्नातानां भारशिवानाम्महाराजश्रीभवनागदौहित्रस्य गौतमीपुत्रस्य पुत्रस्य वाकाटकानाम्म-
- 8 हाराजश्रीरुद्रसेनसूनोः³¹ ³²सत्याज्जवकारुण्यशौर्यविक्रमनयविनयमाहात्म्यधीमत्त्व(त्त्व)-
- 9 ³³पात्रगतभक्तित्वधर्मविजयित्वमनोनैर्मर्त्यादिगुणसमुपेतस्य³⁴ वर्षशतमभिवर्द्धमा-
- 10 नकोशदण्डसाधनसन्तानपुत्रपौत्रिणः³⁵ युधिष्ठिरवृत्तेर्वाकाटकानाम्महाराजश्रीपृथि-

²³ This word is engraved on the left side between the first and the second lines.

²⁴ Read *bhagavata*.

²⁵ It can also be read as *nāgarōjñō = nantasya*. Thus the name of the snake-king might be either Nanna or Ananta both of which are met with in early inscriptions.

²⁶ Before handing these plates over to the Department, the owner tried to get the plates cleaned through a goldsmith. Due to this treatment some portion of the first line has become almost illegible. Hence the reading of this portion is uncertain.

²⁷ Observance of sandhi rules would require *-dhāriṇō dēvā*.

²⁸ Serial number 1 of the plate is engraved here in the left margin a little below.

²⁹ Sandhi has not been observed here; otherwise it would have been spelt as *samrājō*.

³⁰ The observance of sandhi rules would have turned it into *sūnōr = atyanta-* together with the first word in the next line.

³¹ This is an example of *sāpēkṣa samāsa*. Generally we have ... *senasya sūnōh-* in its place in other grants which is correct.

³² Before this expression *atyanta-māhēśvarasya* is noticed in the grants of Pravara-sēna II.

³³ Serial number 2 of the plate is engraved between lines 8 and 9 in the left margin.

³⁴ In other charters we have *guṇais = samuḥētasya* or *guṇa-samuditasya* in the place of the present expression.

³⁵ The application of the sandhi rules would require *-pautriṇō*.

- 11 वि(वी)पेन(ण)सूनोः³⁶ भगवतश्चक्रलक्ष्मप्रतिष्ठितशासनस्य³⁷ वाकाटकानाम्महाराज-
श्रीरुद्रसेनस्य
12 वचनात् [। *] पद्मपुरपूर्वमार्गं अस्मत्सन्तकास्सर्वाद्यक्षनियोगनियुक्ता आज्ञासञ्चारिकुल-

SECOND PLATE : SECOND SIDE

- 13 पुत्राधिकृताः भटाश्छान्नाश्च व्युषि(विश्वु)तपूर्वयाज्ञयाज्ञापितव्या[: । *] विदितमस्तु वः³⁸
यथेहास्माभि-
14 रात्मनो धर्म्मोयुर्बलविजयैश्वर्यविवृद्धये इहामू(सु)त्रहितार्थमात्मानुग्रहाय वैजयिके ध-
15 र्म्मस्थाने कुरुदुम्भकस्य अपरपार्श्वे³⁹ शङ्खिकयोः उत्तरपार्श्वे⁴⁰ बाब्बैकायाः पु(पू)र्व-
16 पार्श्वे फुकुदुम्भकस्य दक्षिणपार्श्वे सेल्लुद्द्रहो नाम ग्राम⁴¹ अच्छभल्लिकानामग्राम-
17 मः सरग्रामकानामग्रामः अरग्रामकानामग्रामः⁴² वात्सगुल्मक(का)र्य-
18 सात्वतचरणाधिवासद्वयस्य⁴³ । अपूर्वदत्या(त्या) उदकपूर्वमतिस्मृष्टः [। *] उचिता(तां)-
श्चास्य
19 ब्राह्मणाना(नां) नानागोत्रचरणात(नां) य⁴⁴ स[चा]य⁴⁵ निरताना(नां)

THIRD PLATE : FIRST SIDE

- 20 पूर्वराज्ञानुमताम्(न्) चातुर्वे(व्वै)द्याग्रहारमर्यादापरिहारान्वितरामः [। *] तद्यथा
21 ⁴⁶अकरदायी अभटच्छ(च्छा)त्रप्रावेश्यः⁴⁷ अपारम्परगोबलि(ली)वर्द्धः अपुष्पक्षीरसन्दो-
22 हः अचारासनचर्म्मार्ङ्गार अलवन(ण)किण्वक्रेणिखनकः सर्वविष्टि-
23 परिहारपरिहृतः सनिधिस्सोपनिधिः सकलसोपकलसः आचन्द्रादित्यकालीय [: *]

³⁶ This is yet another instance of the *sāpēkṣa samāsa*. In other charter we get *Pr̥thivi-*
(*i*)*ṣēṇasya sūnōh*. If the sandhi rules were observed, it would have become
-*sūnōr* = .

³⁷ In the grants of Pravarasēna II and Pr̥thivīṣēṇa II we have instead *Cakrapāṇēh pra-*
sād-ōpārjita-śrī-samudayasya. In this respect this charter may be regarded as
giving an indication of the draft as it existed during the reign of Rudrasēna II.

³⁸ Sandhi, if observed, would require *Vō*.

³⁹ Sandhi would have made it *-sy-ōpara-*.

⁴⁰ The observance of the sandhi rules would require *-kayōr = uttarā*.

⁴¹ Read *-grmō = ccha-*.

⁴² The sandhi rules would require *grāmō*.

⁴³ This happens to be the only punctuation mark employed in the entire inscription and it
happens to be superfluous.

⁴⁴ This letter is superfluous.

⁴⁵ Read *svōdhyāya-*.

⁴⁶ The numeral 3 is engraved here in the left margin below the twenty-first and above the
twenty-second line.

⁴⁷ Here and at a few other places in this as well as the following lines the sandhi rules
have not been observed.

- 24 पुत्रपौत्रानुगामी भुजता(तां) न केनचिद्वयाघात[:*] कर्त्तव्यः [।*] सर्वक्रिया-
भिस्संरक्षि-

THIRD PLATE : SECOND SIDE

- 25 तव्य[:*] परिवर्द्धयितव्यश्च [।*] यश्चास्मच्छासनमगणयमानस्स्वल्पामापि परि-
26 बाधान्कु(कु)र्यात्कारापयित⁴⁸ वा तस्य ब्राह्मणैर्ध्वेदितस्य सदण्डनिग्रहं⁴⁹ कुर्याम [।*]
27 भस्मि(स्मि)श्च धर्मादरकरणे अति(ती)तानै(ने)कराजदत्तनासञ्चितन-
28 परिपालन⁵⁰ कृतपुण्यानुकीर्त्तनपरिहारार्थम् न कीर्त्तयामः [।*]
29 सङ्कल्पाभिद्यो(यो)गपराक्क्रमोपाजतान्वर्त्तमानानाज्ञापयामः [।*]

FOURTH PLATE

- 30 एष्यतत्कालप्रभविष्णु(ष्णु) गौरवान्द्रविष्यान्विज्ञापयामः [।*] व्यासगीता(त)श्चा[त्*]
श्लोकः
31 प्रमाणीकर्त्तव्यः [।*] स्वदत्तां पददत्तां वा यो हरेत वसुधरां(राम्) [।*] गवां
शतसहस्र-
32 स्य हन्तुह(हं)रति दुष्कृतम् [॥१*] सव्वत्सरे⁵¹ पञ्चमे वर्षापक्षे षष्ठ(ष्टे)
33 दिवसे सप्तमे [।*] स(स्व)मुखाज्ञा(ज्ञ)सि⁵² [।*] लिखितं सेनापतिविभि(भी)-
षणेन [।*]
34 ⁵³सिद्धिरस्तुः⁵⁴

⁴⁸ Read *pratibādhām kuryyāt kārayēd.*

⁴⁹ Read *sa-dāṇḍa-nigrahaṁ* or *sa-dāṇḍam nigrahaṁ.*

⁵⁰ Read *atit-ānēka-rāja-datta-sañcītana-paripālanam.*

⁵¹ Read *samvatsarē,*

⁵² Alternatively *-mukh-ājñā* itself would be enough.

⁵³ At the end of the Vaṅgāon plates of Pravarasēna II's twenty-fifth regnal year we have the queer word *mastu* [CII, V (1963), p. 56, line 42] which probably stands for *siddhi=astu*. Mirashi suggests to read *śivam=astu* or *siddham=astu* (*ibid.*, p. 56, fn. 13).

⁵⁴ The sign looks like a *visarga* which is not required. However, as pointed out above, it may have been used as a conclusion mark.